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A novel hybrid catalytic system based on immobilization of phosphomolybdic acid on ionic liquid decorated cyclodextrin-nanosponges: Efficient catalyst for the green synthesis of benzochromeno-pyrazole through cascade reaction: Triply green

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Samahe Sadjadi², Mansoureh Daraie¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran,

² Department of Gas Conversion, Faculty of Petrochemicals, Iran Polymer and Petrochemical Institute, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

An efficient hybrid catalyst was developed by immobilization of Keggin type heteropolyacid, phosphomolybdic acid, in the nanocavities of ionic liquid-modified cyclodextrin nanosponges. This immobilized species was characterized by SEM/EDX, FTIR, TGA, ICP-AES and XRD. The catalytic activity of the hybrid catalyst was confirmed in the synthesis of benzochromeno-pyrazole derivatives via cascade reaction of hydrazine hydrate, ethyl acetoacetate, α or β -naphthol and benzaldehyde. To establish the synergetic effects of conjugation of heteropolyacid and ionic liquid, the catalytic activity of the hybrid catalyst was compared with that of bare ionic liquid-modified cyclodextrin nanosponges. The obtained results indicated the superior activity of the former, from different points of view such as product yield and reaction time. Noteworthy, the catalyst was reusable and could be recovered and reused for several reaction runs. The comparison of obtained results with previous reports was performed. Moreover, the potential utility of the catalyst under ultrasonic and microwave irradiation has been proved.

Keywords: Heteropolyacids, Cyclodextrin nanosponge, Benzochromeno-pyrazole, Catalyst, Cascade reaction.